

Original article

SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING AND THE ROLE OF ACCOUNTANTS: A STRUCTURED LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract: Accountants are responsible for corporate reporting, including the demands of the stakeholders for non-financial information. In this respect, it is considered that the accountants play an important role in relation to their involvement in the sustainability reporting activities. Therefore, the main objective of the present paper is represented by the review of the existing literature on sustainability reporting and the role of accountants in this matter. To provide a clear picture of the academic papers in this field, the structured literature review (SLR) was used as a research method. The findings show that researchers investigated sustainability reporting from three main perspectives: practices related to sustainability reporting; technologies and reporting tools; factors which influence the disclosure / reporting. Our findings reveal that studies related to the role of the accounting profession are limited and most of them envisage accounting systems. Despite this limitation, our research could be of interest to academics as it provides ideas for future research. The summary of the existing literature in this field could also be useful for accounting professionals who are responsible for not only accounting but also reporting on sustainability information. Moreover, the results of this study may be relevant to companies required to disclose such information.

Keywords: sustainability reporting; accountants; structured literature review (SLR); environmental, social, governance (ESG); Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)

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1. Introduction

In the context of a business environment that demands accountants' active involvement in sustainability initiatives (Che Kasim et al., 2024), the main question that arises is related to the role of accountants in these activities. Mainly, accountants are responsible for corporate reporting, including the demands of the stakeholders for non-financial information, playing an important role in the facilitation of sustainability reporting initiatives (Gulo & Octafian, 2024). Therefore, it is considered that the accounting profession should be prepared to respond to the challenges occurring in relation to the environmental, social, governance (ESG) reporting (Cohn, 2021), but also to sustainability reporting in general.

In view of the aforementioned considerations, it was deemed relevant to examine the implications of the accounting profession with respect to sustainability reporting. The main objective of the present paper is to conduct a comprehensive review of the extant literature on the role of accountants in sustainability reporting. To achieve the objective of this study, the following three research questions are addressed:

RQ1: How is research on the role of accountants in sustainability reporting developing?

RQ2: What is the focus and critique of the literature regarding sustainability reporting?

RQ3: What is the future for sustainability reporting research?

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To provide an answer to the above three questions a structured literature review (SLR) was employed as the research method following the specific steps (Massaro et al., 2016). The particularity of the SLR is that papers utilising this approach as a research method do not follow the traditional structure which involves dedicated sections for the literature review and the results of the research. Under the SLR, the literature review represents in fact the findings of the paper. However, it is important to mention that when applying the SLR, the authors should follow rigid rules and design a logical structure, compared with the traditional literature which does not follow certain rules.

The SLR was also applied by other authors in the field of integrated reporting (Dumay et al., 2016). Another study of a similar nature was conducted to analyse the role of management accountants in sustainability accounting and reporting (Ascani et al., 2021). In this respect, this paper synthesises the extant literature in this field with the aim of gaining insight into the current state of knowledge in the area and proposing future research directions. Our paper follows the rules from the aforementioned study, considering the period between 2021 and 2024, while the study mentioned above considered the period between 2001 and 2020 (Ascani et al., 2021). Also, while previous literature (Ascani et al., 2021) analyses only the role of the management accounts, our paper considers the role of the entire accounting profession. Moreover, our study undertakes the review the literature published in this period, considering the recent context related to the European regulations for sustainability reporting.

The paper is organized in accordance with the typical structure of a paper that uses SLR, as follows. As mentioned above, a traditional literature review will not be presented in the next section because the results section of a SLR is represented by the review of the existing papers (Massaro et al., 2016). Thus, the next section, entitled Research method, presents in detail how the SLR steps were applied in the case of our paper. This section is followed by the Results section, where the findings obtained after the application of the SLR and directions for future research are presented. Finally, we provide the main conclusions and limitations of the study.

2. Research method

To understand the contribution and the status of the existing literature in the field of sustainability reporting and the accountants’ role, we have adopted the ten-step method for the writing of a SLR (Massaro et al., 2016). The ten steps are presented in figure 1 below and discussed in detail in this section.

Figure 1: The process to develop a SLR

Source: Adapted from Massaro et al. (2016)

A structured literature review typically commences with the formulation of a **research protocol**. In this initial stage, the authors describe and justify the review question, and the method used, as well as delineating the parameters of the literature search. Considering the significant potential of conducting a SLR in the field of sustainability reporting, with a particular focus on the role of accountants in this context, we initiated the search

process. Given the significant attention that sustainability reporting has received from both researchers and practitioners in recent years, and the mandatory disclosure of specific indicators for certain companies (EU Commission, 2024), a comprehensive search was conducted for articles published between 2021 and 2024. To narrow the scope of our research, we conducted a search within the Scopus database, limiting the subject area to journals in the fields of business, management, and accounting. Conference proceedings and review papers were excluded from our analysis to ensure the quality of the data (Knudsen, 2020). The Scopus database was selected based on its broader journal indexing and extensive use for literature reviews (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016). Thus, we believe that the database under consideration provides a comprehensive overview of the extant literature in this field, as well as studies of a high quality.

After the establishment of the protocol, the second step was to define the **research questions**. These were derived from the generic ones, with adaptations made to align with the specific characteristics of our research field. The first research question is intended to provide an answer regarding the history of the field and the way previous literature contributed to its development. The second research question is aimed to offer answers to the focus and critique of the literature and its evolution. The answers to the last research question seek to provide readers with future research directions in the field. The three research questions of the study are presented in Figure 1.

The third stage of the process involved identifying the type of studies to be included, followed by a comprehensive **literature search**. As presented above, we began the searching process in Scopus database based on keywords in the field of business, management and accounting. By following a previous study (Ascani et al., 2021), which conducted a SLR in a similar field for articles published between 2001 and 2020, we searched for the words: "sustainability", "sustainable practice", "sustainability practice", "sustainable development", "SDG", "sustainable report", "sustainability report", "sustainability reporting", "sustainability accounting", "accountant". Furthermore, the terms "ESG", "ESRS" and "CSRD" were also included in the search, in light of the recent European regulation concerning the disclosure of such information (EU Commission, 2024). The initial search yielded 130 studies, which were subsequently subjected to a rigorous evaluation process to determine their suitability for further analysis. The title of each paper was initially examined to ascertain that all the selected studies included the terms "reporting," "disclosure," "performance," and "accounting". This was done to ensure that the research would focus on the role of accountants in sustainability reporting. Following this, the papers that did not include any of these terms were excluded from the dataset, which then consisted of 57 papers. These papers were then analysed based on their abstracts and another 35 studies were eliminated as their focus was on management, investments, government or other contexts not related to accounting or reporting. The final dataset consisted of 22 papers which were used in further analysis. The details of the selected papers are presented in Appendix A. Of the total number of papers, 12 employ a qualitative approach, 8 of them adopt a quantitative method, while the remaining 2 studies use a combination of methods to present their findings. The same search approach was applied in the Web of Science database, with the initial search returning 50 studies. After examining the titles, only 16 studies were retained. Of these, 14 were eliminated after the abstract examination. However, the remaining 2 studies do not envisage the accounting sector and in this context. Thus, the idea of using the Scopus database was more relevant for the purpose of the present study.

In the fourth step, the **article impact** was evaluated using the number of citations as a proxy for interest (Dumay et al., 2016). The number of citations was collected using the Google Scholar database. At the time of conducting this research, the total number of citations for the analysed papers was 679, indicating a high level of interest in this area. The articles that were most frequently cited (137 times each) were related to sustainability reporting and approaches to materiality (Jørgensen et al., 2022), and to the influence of female directors on ESG reporting (De Masi et al., 2021). Despite the relatively low number of citations received by some of the articles, they were not excluded from the analysis. This was on the grounds that they had recently been published and the period for citing them was limited (Dumay, 2014).

Once the final dataset had been acquired, the **analytical framework** was defined to organize the findings. The unit of analysis was the research topic or focus. Regarding this unit, the following criteria were taken into consideration: practices related to the sustainability reporting, technologies and reporting tools, and factors influencing disclosure/reporting. This was based on the observation that the papers analysed focus on these three areas. Furthermore, it was considered that a more comprehensive understanding of sustainability reporting research could be achieved by dividing the research focus into different items. In addition, for each criterion, the findings and research methods were discussed to ascertain the results of the papers and the methods used for their analysis. Figure 2 shows the distribution of citations on the main themes. As demonstrated in the figure, from the total number of 679 citations, academic papers concerning sustainability reporting received the highest number of citations (302), followed by those related to the factors influencing disclosure and reporting (283 citations), and finally those related

to technologies and reporting tools (94 citations). This finding suggests that practices related to sustainability reporting are of significant interest to researchers in this field.

Figure 2: The distribution of citations on themes

Source: Authors based on Scopus and Google Scholar data

As a sixth step, the **reliability** of the literature review was established by means of separate coding of the reviewed papers, resulting in the identification of a similar analytical unit and criteria.

A further step in the analysis was the testing of the literature review **validity** for each of the three methods (Massaro et al., 2016). To guarantee internal validity, the authors undertook separate coding of the papers. To guarantee external validity, articles were excluded from the analysis if they were irrelevant. These steps are described in more detail in the third step of the analysis. To guarantee construct validity, the analysis of citations was undertaken as discussed in the fourth step.

Subsequently, the **data was coded** in accordance with the aforementioned methodology, with manual coding being employed in the absence of computer-aided assistance.

3. Results

3.1. Insights and critique

The ninth step in conducting a SLR is to provide insights and critique on the existing literature. Therefore, we divided the papers depending on their research focus. As previously stated, the objective of this study was to examine the current state of the literature on the role of accountants in sustainability reporting. However, following the application of the SLR, it was identified that there is a limited number of papers which analyse the role of the accounting profession in relation to sustainability reporting. Most of the studies are concentrated on how different companies report on their sustainability matters. Accordingly, the findings have been organized according to accountants' roles and the issues pertaining to reporting.

- **Practices related to sustainability reporting**

Accountants are responsible for the preparation and dissemination of corporate reports, which encompass both financial and non-financial information demanded by stakeholders. It is therefore evident that the accounting profession plays a pivotal role with respect to sustainability reporting (Gulo & Octafian, 2024). Some studies in our dataset provide information regarding the accounting role in this direction. For example, one of the studies conducted an analysis to ascertain the potential impact of a practical sustainability accounting framework on the transformation of organisational accounting approaches to sustainability (Malik et al., 2021). The findings imply that the accounting profession must take on a more substantial role in sustainability debates by providing assistance and endorsement of associated methodologies and tools. This would enable organisations to assess and disclose a more comprehensive range of performance indicators. Another study set out to ascertain the evolution of research and the relationship between research constituents in the field of biodiversity accounting (Blanco-Zaitegi et al., 2022). The authors employed a quantitative method based on bibliometric analysis to investigate a sample of 63 papers. Regarding the

sustainability cluster, it was proposed that accountants could assume a pivotal role in addressing biodiversity matters due to their capacity to communicate companies' actions.

Another set of studies has been conducted to provide information regarding the sustainability accounting practices. In this respect, authors analysed the sustainability accounting and reporting practices in the Middle East and North Africa regions using document analysis and interviews as research methods (Juusola & Srouji, 2023). Their results indicate that, in these jurisdictions, sustainability reporting faces numerous challenges. One of the most interesting findings show that, in this region, local organizations tend to take sustainability reporting superficially. On the other hand, they implement such initiatives with the aim of benefiting from cost savings or because it is required by governments or clients. Furthermore, another study employed an exploratory methodology to investigate the extent of ESG indicators adoption in 10 Indian banking institutions (Mishra & Sant, 2024). The authors utilised the content of non-financial information reporting as a dataset, categorizing ESG indicators into three pillars: environmental, social and governance matters. The findings indicate that environmental indicators are disclosed with greater frequency than the other categories in both public and private banking institutions.

To identify the non-financial information reported by the financial institutions analysed and their relationship with economic-financial variables, an external analysis and a case study based on semi-structured interviews were employed (Moneva et al., 2023). For the external analysis, they used as a dataset 44 companies located in the European Union (EU) that reported sustainability information in recent years, while for the case study they conducted 10 interviews with representatives of Spanish financial institutions. The results show that the number of integrated reports and their availability increased over time. Also, the complexity of sustainability reporting has grown during the period analysed. With regards to the relationship between non-financial information disclosure and the financial ones, findings show that the accounting for these issues is not associated with the level of income. To identify reporting patterns of corporate social responsibility (CSR) information, one of the studies analysed the reports for 106 Chinese entities for the period 2004 – 2015 (Guo et al., 2023). The results show an increase in the number of CSR reports during the analysed period. However, it is important to note that the information included by entities in the CSR reports does not fulfil the needs of stakeholders. According to the findings, entities applied their own CSR framework, and the lack of unified reports may determine a reduction of the effectiveness and comparability of CSR reporting. Some critical aspects related to the CSR reporting are also identified: the name of the reports varies across companies; entities follow multiple guidelines and regulations; there is a need for improvement in terms of quality and reliability of the information included in the reports.

Other studies in the review present different concerns related to sustainability reporting. For example, one of them analysed the discrepancies and missing elements in the reports of major automobile companies, in the context of the transition to electric vehicles (Molnár et al., 2024). The objective of this paper was to identify a methodology or model that could be incorporated into a possible model framework for sustainability reporting. In this sense, it was considered that from the point of view of sustainability, a model based on product life cycle assessment could bring benefits to the accounting field (facilitating the realization of accounting practices). The authors concluded that reporting requirements should be strengthened so that companies report in a standardized manner, especially information on the determination of CO₂ emissions. On the other hand, previous literature studied sustainability reporting emphasizing some concerns related to the materiality concept (Jørgensen et al., 2022). More specifically, the tensions between the two materiality approaches used in practice are illustrated: the materiality definition provided by the Global Reporting Initiative and the materiality definition according to the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board. The authors investigated the users' perspective in relation to these materiality definitions applying 30 surveys and 6 interviews. The results of the study show that due to different materiality approaches, the users of sustainability reports may register unjustified conclusions. Therefore, more clarity regarding the presentation of the materiality within the non-financial reports is required. To identify the barriers encountered by the small and medium entities when preparing sustainability reports, one of the studies conducted a systematic literature review (Setyaningsih et al., 2024). The authors analysed 37 papers from the period 2012 - 2023 and concluded that the main 6 barriers are: "financial; general attitude; knowledge and technology; organizational; policies and regulations as well as socio-environmental" aspects.

In summary, the extant literature indicates that accountants should occupy an important role not only to report the sustainability information, but also to assist in methodologies and tools of reporting. This allows companies to present a comprehensive array of information pertaining to sustainability, thereby assisting stakeholders in making informed decisions. Moreover, accountants can take the role of communicators in biodiversity matters (Blanco-Zaitegi et al., 2022) but also in other types of information in this field. Nevertheless, the interpretation of sustainability accounting and reporting practices varies across different jurisdictions, with disclosure requirements differing between regions. However, there is a lack of studies in the context of the EU jurisdiction, even in the presence of

increased requirements on sustainability reporting. While only one of the studies highlighted above discusses the role of accountants in the EU context (Moneva et al., 2023), the others refer to countries in Europe outside the EU (one paper) or to different continents and the global level. Moreover, most studies are grounded in qualitative methodologies, with only two studies (Blanco-Zaitegi et al., 2022; Jørgensen et al., 2022), employing a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches. This finding indicates that the role of accountants in the context of sustainability reporting is a multifaceted phenomenon that necessitates a thorough examination. The researchers primarily utilise interviews and annual reports as data sources.

- **Technologies and reporting tools**

The accounting profession has the potential to make a significant contribution to sustainability reporting through the utilisation of diverse reporting tools and technologies, as well as data derived from accounting systems. Our analysis identified studies pertaining to both accounting systems and other technologies and tools. As an example, to incorporate the long-term emission potential into the existing carbon accounting method, one of the studies has proposed a novel double-entry carbon accounting instrument for the evaluation of sustainability and financial risk (Cheung, 2023). The author employed a case study to construct a balance sheet, an income statement, and a cash flow statement that illustrate the carbon emissions and carbon credits. The findings of the study indicate that a company may potentially incur a considerable long-term risk and liability due to its carbon emission potential.

Automation tools and data migration are other important aspects discussed by the authors. For instance, an analysis was conducted on the way different practices and frameworks utilise the data exported from the accounting system for the evaluation and reporting of Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) achievements in local governments from Europe (Cohen et al., 2023). Through the presentation of a comparative analysis of four distinct frameworks, the authors demonstrate that accounting systems are not being employed to their full potential. They argue that the relationship between SDGs and accounting should be strengthened and expanded. In relation to this matter, another study proposes recommendations and justify the feasibility of automation solutions based on data sets and artificial intelligence of corporate sustainability accounting and reporting for improving the product quality management in industry 4.0 (Karbekova et al., 2023). To evaluate the impact of sustainability indicators on product quality and the influence of automation tools on sustainability reporting, the authors employed regression analysis. Additionally, they used correlation analysis to assess the relationship between the artificial intelligence index and sustainability reporting rates. Their findings indicate that corporate sustainability accounting and reporting exert a significant influence on product quality in industry 4.0. Furthermore, automation solutions that are based on artificial intelligence have a notable impact on the advancement of corporate sustainability and reporting practices.

Another set of studies discuss sustainability tools used in reporting. Regarding the ESG reporting, previous literature investigated the relationship between the technologies related to the I5.0 concept and the ESG disclosure and concluded that “I5.0 is particularly useful in enhancing ESG disclosure authenticity, extending ESG disclosure from retrospective to prospective and real-time reporting, customizing ESG reports, extending the scope of reporting to multi-tier supply chains, reducing ESG cost, and enhancing the overall efficacy of ESG disclosure” (Asif et al., 2023). Another study was performed in relation to the corporate sustainability ranking lists reporting tool (Patara & Dhalla, 2022). The authors explored the methodologies applied within three ranking lists and observed “variances in the ranking methodologies” and “inconsistencies in the way sustainability is understood and applied”.

As presented by the authors of the reviewed papers, there is a strong argument to be made for the existence of a relationship between sustainability and accounting. The evaluation and calculation of sustainability are proposed to be based on data extracted from the accounting system. Additionally, the authors posit that automation tools may play a significant role in sustainability reporting. Conversely, numerous sustainability indicators, including carbon footprints, can be reported and calculated in a manner analogous to accounting indicators using balance sheets, income statements, and cash flow statements (Cheung, 2023). This suggests a strong connection between accounting and sustainability. In terms of geographical context, one paper is specifically referring to the European countries, discussing four specific frameworks for SDG reporting (Cohen et al., 2023), while another one only uses a company from an EU country to provide an illustration of the model developed (Cheung, 2023). The remaining publications are not designed to analyse any specific country or to discuss this phenomenon on a global scale. As well as in the previous subsection, most studies utilise a qualitative approach (4 out of 5), thereby demonstrating the intricacies of the subject matter.

- **Factors that influence disclosure / reporting**

Following the application of the SRL, eight papers were identified which analyse the relationship between sustainability reporting and certain factors, but also barriers for its implementation. Regarding sustainability

reporting, most studies focus on the disclosure of SDG and ESG indicators. As an example in this direction, one research paper identified factors that positively influence the disclosure of SDG activities at the level of companies (Bose et al., 2024). These factors include ESG performance ratings, the presence of stakeholder engagement practices within firms and the preparation of standalone sustainability reports (this means that entities do not include non-financial information within the financial reports but prepare a separate sustainability report). In addition, the relationship between the SDG disclosure and the corporate ESG performance of companies was analysed (Nicolo' et al., 2024). In this respect, the authors used a sample of 635 entities situated in 45 countries. The study was performed considering data from the period 2016 – 2020. To measure the level of the SDG disclosure, an index was computed. Applying a regression analysis, the authors concluded that ESG performance positively affects the SDG disclosure. Studies have also investigated different factors that influence sustainability reporting (Paridhi & Ritika, 2024). The application of regression methods by authors resulted in the identification of several factors, including resource availability, political stability, awareness synergises for progress, administrative efficiency and performance factors. On the other hand, a recent study investigated whether the number of women on board of entities influences the ESG disclosure (De Masi et al., 2021). In this respect, the study used data from a sample of companies listed in Italy during 2005-2017 and applied a regression model. The results show that the level of ESG disclosure is positively influenced by the number of women on board. Moreover, according to the authors, the presence of women on board has a “positive influence on every component of the ESG score”.

Other studies in our literature review discuss the relationship between sustainability reporting and investments. In this respect, the relationship between investment efficiency and ESG reporting using a sample of sustainability reports consisting of 448 Indonesian non-financial listed firm-year observations in the period 2010-2018 was investigated (Harymawan et al., 2022). The results of this study indicated that investment efficiency has a significant impact on the quality of ESG reporting. Furthermore, another research paper analysed the relationship between high quality sustainability reporting and sustainable and responsible investment using a sample of 77 equity funds from Thomson Reuters (D'Apice et al., 2021). Their results show that the improvement of sustainability disclosure significantly influences the sustainable and responsible investment funds intensity. Similarly, previous literature investigated the relationship between corporate sustainability and total shareholder returns through regression analysis, utilizing a dataset comprising 944 firm-year observations from Nordic capital markets (Lueg & Pesheva, 2021). In this study, the term 'corporate sustainability' is used to encompass both sustainability reporting and sustainable management practices. The findings indicate that corporate sustainability has a positive effect on total shareholder returns, even in small capital markets such as those in the Nordic countries. In addition, the authors found that the companies analysed disclose an excessive amount of information on sustainability matters, which increases their agency costs and consequently reduces the total shareholder return.

Finally, to investigate the barriers to social responsibility accounting implementation and the strategies associated with this issue, one of the reviewed papers effectuated a study based on literature, interviews with six academic experts and interpretive structural modelling (Khodamipour et al., 2024). They identified four groups of barriers namely organizational, executive, social and accounting profession. Of the 12 barriers discussed in the paper, “lack of public awareness of the importance of social responsibility accounting, lack of social responsibility accounting implementation regulations and organisation size” were found to be the significant ones. The results also showed that the most effective strategies to combat social responsibility accounting implementation barriers are “mandatory regulations, the introduction of guidelines and social responsibility accounting standards”, “regulatory developments and government incentive schemes to implement social responsibility accounting” as well as “increasing public awareness of the benefits of social responsibility accounting”.

In summary, the studies on the factors influencing sustainability reporting have identified ESG performance as a factor that positively influences SDG reporting, as shown by two of the papers reviewed. In addition, the disclosure of SDG indicators is influenced by stakeholder engagement practices within companies and the preparation of standalone sustainability reports. Also, the quality of sustainability reporting may be influenced by the availability of resources, the prevailing political stability, the level of awareness, the synergy for progress, the efficiency and performance of the administrative factor, and the number of women on the board. The quality of sustainability reporting is also influenced by the level of investment, while having a significant impact on shareholder value. Moreover, the authors of the reviewed papers conclude that there are three main barriers to the implementation of social responsibility accounting, but also effective strategies to overcome these barriers. However, it should be noted that most of the extant research on this topic is based on a global or regional context outside the EU. At the level of the EU, only two papers are addressing the factors that influence the reporting of sustainability information (De Masi et al., 2021; Lueg & Pesheva, 2021). Having that the impact can be measured through the implementation

of empirical analysis, a total of seven out of eight studies has been carried out using a quantitative approach. The majority of these are focusing on regression analysis of data obtained from research databases.

3.2. Future research directions

The final step in conducting an SLR is to provide future research directions and avenues based on the discussion in relation to the existing literature. As presented in the previous subsection, there are relatively few studies on the role of accountants in sustainability reporting. Therefore, we suggest that researchers direct their attention in this area, especially at the EU level, as accountants are the main providers of information for decision making. Specifically, future work could investigate who is responsible for providing such information in different companies and different countries, and what information accountants should provide and why. Researchers could also analyse whether universities and professional organizations are preparing students for this practice and how this topic is included in their curricula.

In terms of technology and reporting tools, future studies could further investigate how companies are automating the process of preparing sustainability reports and suggest tools for presenting this information. In this regard, the opinion of professionals in the field should be sought to find out how the information is gathered and disclosed. Based on their opinions, researchers could propose recommendations to improve the process. In addition, other studies could explore whether the systems used by companies could be seen as an obstacle to providing such information and the costs associated with producing these reports in terms of technology and automation tools.

Regarding the factors influencing the reporting of sustainability issues, future studies could investigate whether factors other than those mentioned in the reviewed papers could be considered as influencing disclosure. For example, researchers could focus on issues of information asymmetry and determine whether this factor applies to companies that are not required to disclose such information. Other studies could assess the impact of the factors mentioned in the reviewed papers by controlling for industry, company size and other significant aspects.

4. Conclusions

The main objective of the present study was to provide a review of the most recent extant literature on sustainability reporting and accountants' role in this matter, using SLR as a research method. Therefore, this study provides directions for future research in this area. The results obtained from the research indicate that the investigation of sustainability reporting was conducted from three distinct perspectives: firstly, practices related to the sustainability reporting; secondly, technologies and reporting tools; and thirdly, factors influencing the disclosure/reporting.

In terms of practices related to the sustainability reporting, a proportion of the studies is concentrated on the development of a model framework for sustainability reporting, sustainability accounting and reporting practices, the identification of issues for the materiality concepts and on the identification of barriers encountered by entities when preparing the sustainability reports. Only a small part from the studies envisages the role of the accountants in the sustainability reporting, as follows: (1) accountants could assume a pivotal role in addressing biodiversity matters due to their communication role regarding companies' actions; (2) the accounting profession must take on a more substantial role in sustainability debates by providing assistance and endorsement of associated methodologies and tools, thus enabling organizations to assess and disclose a more comprehensive range of performance indicators. In relation to the technologies and reporting tools, studies have demonstrated that the accounting systems are not being utilised to their maximum capacity for the purpose of sustainability reporting. Furthermore, automation solutions that are based on artificial intelligence have a notable impact on the advancement of corporate sustainability and reporting practices. Regarding the factors that influence the disclosure/reporting, most studies are concentrated on the SDG or ESG disclosure. The principal factors identified are the presence of stakeholder engagement practices in firms; ESG performance ratings; the number of women on board; investment efficiency. Despite rigorous investigation, no factor related to the accounting profession was identified.

Considering the above, there could be concluded that the number of papers on the role of accountants in sustainability reporting is limited. The extant literature focuses on the practice itself and the factors that influence it. Only a small number of papers discuss the implications of the accounting profession for sustainability reporting, and the aspects related to the accounting systems. Given the new requirements on sustainability reporting, particularly within the EU, accountants are expected to play a pivotal role in facilitating the disclosure of this information. In this respect, accounting education encompassing both university level and professional bodies assumes a crucial role in providing the future practitioners with the necessary skills to maintain the relevance of the profession. As demonstrated by the literature analysed, accountants should possess good communication skills but also technical skills to assist in methodologies and tools of reporting and to extract the necessary sustainability information.

Although accounting professionals are known for their role as information providers to stakeholders, some technical skills related to sustainability may remain uncovered by their expertise. Therefore, communication between accountants and ESG specialists becomes essential for the future of sustainability reporting.

Our research may be of interest to accounting professionals specialising in sustainability reporting, as well as to companies required to disclose sustainability information. Given the comprehensive requirements, companies should adapt their information systems to integrate ESG aspects in addition to financial indicators. The field of sustainability provides novel challenges for the accounting professionals. Defining and accounting for non-financial indicators represent a significant step in the development of the accounting profession. Although audits of sustainability reports are currently voluntary, it is recommended that accounting professionals be prepared to assist or engage in these activities.

A potential limitation of the present research is the identification of a limited number of papers which analyse the role of the accounting profession in relation to sustainability reporting. Other studies could be conducted to provide a similar analysis using alternative databases to extract relevant papers and to include proceeding papers. Despite its limitations, our study makes a significant contribution to the existing literature by offering a comprehensive summary and synthesis of the findings in sustainability reporting, thereby providing academics with valuable ideas for future research.

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Appendix. Dataset details

Ref. No.	Authors (Year)	Title	Journal	Research method	Citations Google S.
1	Molnár P.; Suta A.; Tóth Á. (2024)	Sustainability accounting for greenhouse gas emissions measurement using the GREET LCA model: practical review of automotive ESG reporting	Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy	GREET model	1
2	Asif M.; Searcy C.; Castka P. (2023)	ESG and Industry 5.0: The role of technologies in enhancing ESG disclosure	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	Conceptual analysis	57
3	Guo Y.; Yeh T.-T.; Yang D.C.; Li X.-Y. (2023)	Corporate social responsibility reporting in China: the case of 106 central enterprises	Journal of Global Responsibility	Content analysis	3
4	Bose S.; Khan H.Z.; Bakshi S. (2024)	Determinants and consequences of sustainable development goals disclosure: International evidence	Journal of Cleaner Production	Regression	14
5	Patara S.; Dhalla R. (2022)	Sustainability reporting tools: Examining the merits of sustainability rankings	Journal of Cleaner Production	Content and thematic analysis	9
6	Nicolo' G.; Zampone G.; De Iorio S.; Sannino G. (2024)	Does SDG disclosure reflect corporate underlying sustainability performance? Evidence from UN Global Compact participants	Journal of International Financial Management and Accounting	Regression	21
7	Juusola K.; Srouji R. (2023)	Challenges associated with sustainability accounting and reporting practices: a legitimacy perspective	International Journal of Law and Management	Exploratory qualitative research	12
8	Setyaningsih S.; Widjojo R.; Kelle P. (2024)	Challenges and opportunities in sustainability reporting: a focus on small and medium enterprises (SMEs)	Cogent Business and Management	Systematic literature review	5
9	Jørgensen S.; Mjøs A.; Pedersen L.J.T. (2022)	Sustainability reporting and approaches to materiality: tensions and potential resolutions	Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal	Empirical insights	137
10	Paridhi; Ritika (2024)	Sustainability reporting for boosting national commitment and overcoming challenges: A hierarchical model	Business Strategy and Development	TISM	4
11	Blanco-Zaitegi G.; Álvarez Etxeberria I.; Moneva J.M. (2022)	Biodiversity accounting and reporting: A systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis	Journal of Cleaner Production	Systematic literature review	42
12	Cohen S.; Manes-Rossi F.; Brusca I. (2023)	Are SDGs being translated into accounting terms? Evidence from European cities	Public Money and Management	Comparative analysis	17
13	Moneva J.M.; Scarpellini S.; Aranda-Usón A.; Alvarez Etxeberria I. (2023)	Sustainability reporting in view of the European sustainable finance taxonomy: Is the financial sector ready to disclose circular economy?	Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management	Descriptive analysis	37

14	Harymawan I.; Nasih M.; Agustia D.; Putra F.K.G.; Djajadikerta H.G. (2022)	Investment efficiency and environmental, social, and governance reporting: Perspective from corporate integration management	Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management	Correlation and regression	46
15	Mishra P.; Sant T.G. (2024)	Examine the level of environmental, social and governance disclosure in sustainability report – a study of the Indian banking sector	International Journal of Innovation Science	Content analysis	12
16	Karbekova A.B.; Makhkamova S.G.; Inkova N.A.; Pakhomova O.K. (2023)	Automation based on datasets and ai of corporate accounting and sustainability reporting in quality management in industry 4.0	Proceedings on Engineering Sciences	Regression	10
17	Cheung H. (2023)	Non-monetary double-entry carbon accounting method for entities in emission trading systems	Journal of Cleaner Production	Case study	1
18	Khodamipour A.; Yazdifar H.; Askari Shahamabad M.; Khajavi P. (2024)	Modeling barriers to social responsibility accounting (SRA) and ranking its implementation strategies to support sustainable performance – a study in an emerging market	Journal of Modelling in Management	ISM, TOPSIS	5
19	D'Apice V.; Ferri G.; Intonti M. (2021)	Sustainable disclosure versus ESG intensity: Is there a cross effect between holding and SRI funds?	Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management	Regression	24
20	De Masi S.; Słomka-Gołębiowska A.; Becagli C.; Paci A. (2021)	Toward sustainable corporate behavior: The effect of the critical mass of female directors on environmental, social, and governance disclosure	Business Strategy and the Environment	Regression	137
21	Malik A.; Egan M.; du Plessis M.; Lenzen M. (2021)	Managing sustainability using financial accounting data: The value of input-output analysis	Journal of Cleaner Production	Input-output analysis	53
22	Lueg R.; Pesheva R. (2021)	Corporate sustainability in the Nordic countries – The curvilinear effects on shareholder returns	Journal of Cleaner Production	Regression	32

Source: Authors based on Scopus and Google Scholar data